

Studies in Chromones and Flavones. Part IX.*

Studies on 6- and 7-Methylflavone

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6- and 7-Methylflavone on bromination with NBS gave the 6- and 7-bromomethyl derivative respectively. Organic bases have been prepared from these by condensation with morpholine and dimethylamine. The bromomethyl derivatives have also been converted into the cyanomethyl derivatives which have been hydrolysed to the corresponding acids. These acids on condensation with salicylaldehyde gave 6- and 7-(3'-coumarinyl) flavone.

The bromomethyl derivatives on heating with hexamine gave 6- and 7-formylflavone which on Perkin acetylation gave β -(6-flavonyl)- and β -(7-flavonyl) acrylic acid. β -(6-Flavonyl) alanine and β -(7-flavonyl) alanine have been synthesised from the formylflavones through the intermediate oxazolon derivatives. 6-Formylflavone has also been condensed with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and the vinyl ketone obtained converted into 6-(2'-chromonyl) flavone by heating with selenium dioxide.

EXTENSIVE work has been done on the hydroxy flavones but the studies on alkylflavones have been fewer. It was therefore thought of interest to study some reactions on 6- and 7-methylflavone.

6- and 7-Methylflavone have been synthesised by different workers by different methods¹⁻⁴. In the present work they were prepared as follows:

2-Benzoyloxy-5-methylacetophenone⁵ was subjected to Baker-Venkataraman transformation according to the modification of Looker *et al.*⁶ and the β -diketone obtained was cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid to 6-methylflavone. 7-Methylflavone was synthesised from 2-benzoyloxy-4-methylacetophenone⁷ by a similar procedure.

6- and 7-Methylflavones were converted into 6- and 7-bromomethylflavone by reaction with N-bromosuccinimide in the presence of benzoyl peroxide. These were converted into the corresponding acetoxy-methylflavones by heating with acetic anhydride and freshly fused sodium acetate. Organic bases have been prepared from the bromomethylflavones by reaction with secondary amines such as morpholine and dimethylamine as these are potential CNS stimulants.

6- and 7-Bromomethylflavone on condensation with aqueous potassium cyanide gave the corresponding 6- and 7-cyanomethylflavone. The hydrolysis of these with sulphuric acid gave 6- and 7-carboxymethylflavone. The ethyl esters of these on condensation with salicylaldehyde in the presence of piperidine afforded 6-(3'-coumarinyl) flavone (I) and 7-(3'-coumarinyl) flavone (II) respectively. These are of interest as very few coumarin derivatives with such oxygen heterocyclic ring systems in 3-position are known.

On reaction with hexamine in glacial acetic acid 6- and 7-bromomethylflavone gave 6- and 7-formyl-

flavone respectively. These formylflavones on Perkin acetylation gave β -(6-flavonyl) and β -(7-flavonyl) acrylic acid respectively.

As only a few α -aminoacids are known with a heterocyclic nucleus, it was thought of interest to condense 6- and 7-formylflavone with hippuric acid in the presence of acetic anhydride and freshly fused sodium acetate to get the corresponding azlactone derivatives. These have been converted into

β -(6-flavonyl) alanine (III) and β -(7-flavonyl) alanine (IV) by heating with red phosphorus and hydriodic

acid. With a view to confirm this a similar condensation of 6-formylflavone with acetyl glycine was carried out. It gave an azlactone derivative which on heating with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus gave β -(6-flavonyl) alanine (III) described above.

On condensation with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide, 6-formylflavone gave β -(6-flavonyl) vinyl-*o*-hydroxyphenylketone. The ketone afforded the corresponding acetoxy derivative indicating that the hydroxyl group was free and that no cyclization had taken place.

Cyclodehydrogenation of β -(6-flavonyl) vinyl *o*-hydroxyphenylketone by refluxing with selenium dioxide in iso amyl alcohol gave 6-(2'-chromonyl) flavone (V) which was found identical on direct comparison with that obtained from 3'-acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone by condensation with benzaldehyde and heating the vinyl ketone obtained with selenium dioxide.⁸

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-5-methyl dibenzoyl methane: 2-Benzoyloxy-5-methylacetophenone⁵ (1 g.) was dissolved in dry pyridine (5 ml.) and powdered potassium hydroxide (3 g.) was added with shaking. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 4 hr. and then poured in ice cold hydrochloric acid. The product obtained crystallised from petroleum ether in yellow shining plates (0.8 g.), m.p. 96°. It was soluble in alkali and gave dark brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 75.60; H, 5.68. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.60; H, 5.50%).

Cyclisation: The above β -diketone (1 g.) was kept with conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml.) at room temperature for 4 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture on ice crystallised from petroleum ether in white woolly needles (1 g.), m.p. 122°-23°. Ruhemann³ who prepared it by a different method gave the same melting point.

6-Bromomethylflavone: N-Bromosuccinimide (6 g.) was dissolved in hot dry benzene (200 ml.) and 6-methylflavone (5 g.) dissolved in dry benzene (30 ml.) along with benzoyl peroxide (0.5 g.) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 6 hr. Benzene was removed and water added. The product obtained crystallised from benzene. M.P. 175°. Yield 4.5 g. (Found: Br, 24.71. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2Br$ requires Br, 24.61%).

6-Acetoxyethylflavone: 6-Bromomethylflavone (1 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (2 g.) for 2 hr. The product obtained crystallised from benzene in tiny needles, m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 73.88; H, 4.86. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.46; H, 4.80%).

6-Morpholinomethylflavone hydrochloride: 6-Bromomethylflavone (1 g.) in dry benzene (5 ml.) was refluxed with morpholine (1 ml.) on a steam bath for 2 hr. The product remaining after the removal of benzene was taken in dry ether (20 ml.) and hydrogen chloride gas passed through it for 10 min. The separated solid crystallised from alcohol in shining white crystals, m.p. 293°-94°. (Found: C, 66.99;

H, 5.23; N, 3.73; Cl, 9.55. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3NCl$ requires C, 67.13; H, 5.56; N, 3.91; Cl, 9.70%).

6-Dimethylaminomethylflavone hydrochloride: Prepared from 6-bromomethylflavone (1 g.) and dimethylamine solution (2 ml.) as above and crystallised from alcohol gave m.p. 256°. (Found: C, 68.00; H, 5.51; N, 4.95; Cl, 10.90. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2NCl$ requires C, 68.40; H, 5.70; N, 4.40; Cl, 11.00%).

6-Cyanomethylflavone: A mixture of 6-bromomethylflavone (1 g.) and potassium cyanide (1 g.) in alcohol (100 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 3 hr. It was then poured in ice water and the separated product was crystallised from dilute alcohol in tiny yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 165°. (Found: C, 77.75; H, 4.00; N, 5.43. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2N$ requires C, 78.16; H, 4.21; N, 5.36%).

6-Carboxymethylflavone: 6-Cyanomethylflavone (1 g.) was heated with 70% sulphuric acid solution (10 ml.) on a steam bath for 4 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water was purified through sodium bicarbonate extraction. It crystallised from acetic acid in shining needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 225°. (Found: C, 72.95; H, 4.04. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.85; H, 4.28%).

6-Carboethoxymethylflavone: The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed gently with 10% alcoholic sulphuric acid (25 ml.) for 5 hr. The product obtained crystallised from dilute alcohol in tiny needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 105°. (Found: C, 74.25; H, 5.49. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.00; H, 5.19%).

6-(3'-Coumarinyl) flavone: A mixture of the above ester (1 g.) and salicylaldehyde (2 ml.) in absolute alcohol (7 ml.) was heated under reflux with two drops of piperidine on a steam bath for 4 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in ice cold hydrochloric acid was washed with sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from dilute alcohol. M.P. 257°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 78.25; H, 3.55. $C_{24}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 78.68; H, 3.82%).

6-Formylflavone: A mixture of 6-bromomethylflavone (1 g.) and hexamine (4 g.) in glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 15 min. Hydrochloric acid (1 : 1; 10 ml.) was then added and the heating continued for further 10 min. The product which separated on dilution of the reaction mixture with water crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow tiny needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 186°. (Found: C, 76.76; H, 3.71. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 76.79; H, 4.03%).

The 2,4-D.N.P. was prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene. M.P. 335° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.75. $C_{22}H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.02%).

β -(6-Flavonyl) acrylic acid: 6-Formylflavone (1 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (3 g.) in an oil bath at 170°-80° for 12 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water was purified through sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from nitrobenzene in white shining needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 266°-67°. It decolourised neutral potassium permanganate and bromine water. (Found: C, 73.82; H, 4.07. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 73.96; H, 4.14%).

4-(6'-Flavonyl)-2-phenyl-5-oxazolone : An intimate mixture of 6-formylflavone (1.5 g.) fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) hippuric acid (3 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 ml.) was warmed on a wire gauze till a clear solution was obtained. The bright yellow liquid mixture was heated on a steam bath for 1 hr. Alcohol (15 ml.) was added to the reaction mixture and it was heated for further $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The yellow product which separated on cooling crystallised from benzene in yellowish orange woolly needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 230°-32°. (Found : C, 76.17; H, 3.73; N, 3.56. $C_{25}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 76.33; H, 3.84; N, 3.56%).

β -(6-Flavonyl) alanine : To a mixture of the above oxazolone derivative (1 g.), purified red phosphorus (0.8 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.), hydriodic acid (5 ml. sp. gr. 1.56, 50%) was added in portions with stirring. The reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. It was then filtered and the residue on the filter paper cone was washed with 2 ml. portion of glacial acetic acid. The product separating from the combined filtrates was filtered and treated with sodium bisulphite solution to remove iodine. The decolourised product was then kept with ammonia (10 ml.; 10%) for some time and the clear solution was then neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid to congo red. The product obtained crystallised from distilled water. M.P. 245° (efferv.). It was found to be soluble in hydrochloric acid. It gave a positive ninhydrin test. (Found : C, 70.09; H, 4.76; N, 4.53. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 69.90; H, 4.85; N, 4.53%).

4-(6'-Flavonyl)-2-methyl-5-oxazolone : An intimate mixture of 6-formylflavone (1.5 g.) acetyl glycine (3 g.) freshly fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 ml.) was heated on a steam bath. The product obtained on working up the reaction mixture as before crystallised from xylene. M.P. 254°-55° (decomp.). (Found : C, 72.61; H, 3.73; N, 4.26. $C_{20}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 72.50; H, 3.96; N, 4.23%).

β -(6-Flavonyl) alanine was prepared from the above oxazolone derivative by heating with red phosphorus and hydriodic acid as before. M.P. and mixed m.p. with β -(6-flavonyl) alanine described above was 245° (efferv.).

β -(6-Flavonyl) vinyl-*o*-hydroxyphenylketone : To a solution of 6-formylflavone (2.6 g.) and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (1.3 ml.) in alcohol, potassium hydroxide (5 g. in 5 ml. water) was added. After keeping the reaction mixture overnight it was diluted with ice water and acidified with con. hydrochloric acid. The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid in yellow shining woolly needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 226°. It gave red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and dark orange colour with con. sulphuric acid. Moreover, it gave a positive Wilson test. (Found : C, 78.48; H, 4.07. $C_{24}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 78.26; H, 4.35%).

The acetoxy derivative : The above ketone (0.5 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (2 g.) for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow

needles, m.p. 155°. (Found : C, 76.21. H, 4.15. $C_{26}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 76.09; H, 4.39%).

2-(6'Flavonyl) chromone : The above hydroxy ketone (1 g.) was refluxed in dry iso-amyl alcohol (15 ml.) with selenium dioxide (3 g.) in an oil bath at 140°-50° for 18 hr. It was filtered hot. The product obtained on cooling the filtrate crystallised from benzene in small white needles, m.p. 265°. (Found : C, 78.69; H, 3.51. $C_{24}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 78.68; H, 3.82%).

Mixed m.p. with 2-(6'-Flavonyl) chromone synthesised from 3'-acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone and benzaldehyde⁸ was not depressed.

2-Benzoyloxy-4-methylacetophenone : 2-Hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone⁷ (5 ml.) in pyridine (10 ml.) was shaken with benzoyl chloride (5 ml.) for 15 min at room temperature. Dilute hydrochloric acid was then added. The separated oily layer was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was washed successively with sodium bicarbonate solution, sodium hydroxide solution and finally with water. The thick liquid obtained after evaporating ether was kept overnight in a desiccator for drying. The liquid was used directly for further reaction.

2-Hydroxy-4-methyl dibenzoyl methane : A mixture of the above ketone (1 ml.) in dry pyridine (2 ml.) and powdered potassium hydroxide (4 g.) was kept at room temperature for 4 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in ice cold hydrochloric acid was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water. It crystallised from petroleum ether in yellow shining needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 90°-91°. It was soluble in alkali and gave dark brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 75.56; H, 5.45. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.57; H, 5.55%).

Cyclisation : The above β -diketone (1 g.) was kept with concentrated sulphuric acid (5 ml.) at room temperature for 4 hr. and then poured on ice. The product obtained crystallised from petroleum ether in white shining prisms (0.7 g.), m.p. 120°. Robertson *et al.*⁴ who prepared it by a different method gave the same melting point.

7-Bromomethylflavone : To N-bromosuccinimide (6 g.) dissolved in hot dry benzene (200 ml.), 7-methylflavone (5 g.) and benzoyl peroxide (0.5 g.) in benzene were added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 6 hr. The product obtained on removal of benzene crystallised from benzene. M.P. 166°-67°. Yield 3 g. (Found : Br, 25.05. $C_{26}H_{11}O_2Br$ requires Br, 24.61%).

7-Acetoxy-methylflavone : A mixture of 7-bromo-methylflavone (1 g.), acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (2 g.) was refluxed for 2 hr. The product obtained crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in tiny needles. M.P. 120°-21. (Found : C, 73.53; H, 4.81. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.46; H, 4.80%).

7-Morpholinomethylflavone : Prepared from 7-bromomethylflavone (1 g.) and morpholine by refluxing in benzene for 2 hr and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether gave m.p. 127°-28°. (Found :

C, 74.66; H, 5.88; N, 4.29. $C_{20}H_{19}O_3N$ requires C, 74.76; H, 5.91; N, 4.36%.

7-Dimethylaminomethylflavone: Prepared from 7-bromomethylflavone (1 g.) and dimethylamine solution in benzene and crystallised from petroleum ether in long white needles gave m.p. 98°. (Found: C, 77.16; H, 5.76; N, 4.86. $C_{18}H_{10}O_2N$ requires C, 77.42; H, 6.09; N, 5.02%.)

7-Carboxymethylflavone: 7-Bromomethylflavone (1 g.) in alcohol (100 ml.) was refluxed with potassium cyanide (1 g.) dissolved in minimum quantity of water on a steam bath for 3 hr. The separated cyanomethyl derivative (1 g.) was directly hydrolysed by heating with 90% sulphuric acid (10 ml.) on a steam bath for 4 hr. The acid obtained crystallised from dilute acetic acid. M.P. 220°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 72.74; H, 4.04. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.85; H, 4.28%.)

7-Carboethoxymethylflavone: The above acid (0.4 g.) was refluxed gently with 10% alcoholic sulphuric acid (25 ml.) on a wire gauze for 5 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. It crystallised from dilute acetic acid in white woolly needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 102°-3°. (Found: C, 74.33; H, 5.28. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.00; H, 5.19%.)

7-(3'-Coumarinyl) flavone: A mixture of the above ester (1 g.) and salicylaldehyde (2 ml.) in absolute alcohol (7 ml.) was heated under reflux with two drops of piperidine on a steam bath. The product obtained as working up as usual crystallised from alcohol in white tiny needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 252°. (Found: C, 79.07; H, 3.76. $C_{24}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 78.68; H, 3.82%.)

7-Formylflavone: 7-Bromomethylflavone (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 ml.) and refluxed with hexamine (4 g.) for 15 min. Hydrochloric acid (1 : 1; 10 ml.) was added to the reaction mixture and the heating continued for further 10 min. The product which separated on dilution of the reaction mixture with water crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow woolly needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 179°-80°. (Found: C, 76.45; H, 4.29. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 76.76; H, 4.03%.)

The 2,4-D.N.P.: Prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene gave m.p. 300° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.44; $C_{22}H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.02%.)

β -(7-Flavonyl) acrylic acid: 7-Formylflavone (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) in an oil bath at 170°-80° for 12 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual crystallised from acetic acid. M.P. 302°-3°. Yield 0.6 g. It decolourised neutral potassium

permanganate and bromine water. (Found: C, 74.18; H, 4.13. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 73.96; H, 4.14%.)

4-(7'-Flavonal)2-phenyl-5-oxazolone: An intimate mixture of 7-formylflavone (1.5 g.), freshly fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.), hippuric acid (3 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 ml.) was warmed on a wire gauze till a clear solution was obtained. The bright yellow liquid mixture was then heating on a steam bath for 1 hr. Alcohol (15 ml.) was then added to the reaction mixture and the heating continued further for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The yellow product which separated crystallised from xylene in light yellow needles (0.9 g.), m.p. 280°. (Found: C, 76.35; H, 3.56; N, 3.58. $C_{25}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 76.33; H, 3.84; N, 3.56%.)

β -(7-Flavonyl) alanine: To a mixture of the above oxazolone derivative (1 g.), purified red phosphorus (0.8 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.), hydriodic acid (5 ml.) (1.56 d, 50%) was added in portions with stirring and the reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. It was then filtered and the residue on the filter paper was washed with 2 ml. portions of glacial acetic acid. The product separating from the combined filtrates was filtered and treated with sodium bisulphite solution to remove iodine. The decolourised product was then kept with ammonia (10 ml.; 10%) for some time and the clear solution was then neutralised to congo red with dilute hydrochloric acid. The product obtained crystallised from distilled water. M.P. 225° (efferv.). It was soluble in concentrated hydrochloric acid and gave a positive ninhydrin test. (Found: C, 69.77; H, 4.55; N, 4.13. $C_{18}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 69.90; H, 4.85; N, 4.53%.)

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